

Dutch Design Education: A new approach to design for emotions

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Abstract

This article describes a new educational model on design for emotion in the landscape of Dutch design institutes. The proposed method enhances the emotional literacy of students as a key professional competency - it teaches them to design for emotions. The underlying assumption is that to design for emotions, one should be able to understand and control his own emotions. This model has been applied in the minor Experience Branding (n=37). Students' experiences are reported and reflected upon. Our results show valuable insights. However, we ask to what extent these effects are dependent on mentality of Dutch people.

Conference theme: Emotion in Design Education

Keywords: Dutch design education, design for emotions, emotional literacy

Introduction

In general, higher design education in the Netherlands is characterised by either schooling students in science (Design Research) or training students for a certain profession (Design Education), resulting in students being either researchers or practitioners. Recently, this distinction has been formalised by referring to the former institutions as university and to the latter as a university of applied science; another difference is that full universities automatically cater for the broad palette of students, e.g., bachelor, Master and PhD students, whereas the bachelor students are at the heart of the university of applied science. Most design education emphasises the bachelor phase and can be found at universities of applied science. This is also true for art and design education, which is often situated within art academies. Traditionally design education at Master level has been limited to the three universities of technology located in Eindhoven, Delft and Enschede (i.e., TU/e, TUD, and UT) emphasising the technological background such as knowledge of materials, whereas art academies are to stimulate the development of one's personality, talent and ambitions in order to find their own unique way to contribute to the design landscape.

In our curriculum, we cultivate this personal development while educating professionals in human-centered design. More specifically, we not only emphasise individual development, but also stress the added value designers will bring to the community as a whole. Our approach, described in the remainder of this article, demonstrates that individual development and designing for the real world are intertwined. In order to design in a true human-centered way, both individual personal development and understanding and awareness of others' values are necessary. Therefore, an educational method is presented aiming to develop emotional literacy of students as a professional competency to design for emotions.

Emotional design: current curriculum

The course in focus is Communication & Multimedia Design (CMD), one of six different bachelor courses that are offered at the Institute for Communication, Media and Information Technology (CMI) of the Rotterdam University of Applied Science. Students are trained to design multimedia products and design is the core of the curriculum, supported by subjects such as marketing and (technical) programming. In a user-centered approach, students are trained to focus on the user rather than their personal opinion or ideas about the design profession. The educational method for design for emotions in this article however, emphasises the awareness and personal development of the student in particular.

The educational model has been applied in the minor Experience Branding, one of CMD's graduation courses in which currently 37 students are educated as designers for meaningful brand experiences. The minor takes place in the last two years of the four-years course. The minor involves two teachers with a background in design and marketing. In four periods of ten weeks, students ought to study sixteen hours per week on their own and they have to attend one four-hour class per week. In class, teachers provide lectures and presentations, discussions, and coaching of students in their study assignments. Students receive several study assignments per period to work on for about 10 to 40 hours per assignment. Two course books are prescribed, and students receive a reader with texts related to Experience Branding. Also, a catalogue of images is used to provide visual examples. All students own a laptop with the latest graphical software applications.

The curriculum of the minor is derived from the domains of design, marketing and psychology. It assumes that to be meaningful, a brand should adapt to the individual's norms and values (Shedroff, Diller & Rhea, 2006). And, because what we value evokes the strongest emotions (Modell, 2006), students are challenged to investigate the values underlying their own emotions, as well as the values and emotions of others, in order to deliver meaningful products and services to people using their design competencies. Students develop aesthetic ability and the instrumental knowledge and skills to create desirable and attractive designs, but more importantly, they need to develop their emotional literacy as professional competency and the accompanying knowledge and skills, to create designs which are meaningful to people.

As in most art and design education, students are guided to develop their (visual) aesthetic literacy to perceive and create 'beauty'. Students are also trained in knowledge and skills to make designs themselves. These knowledge and skills are instrumental, in the sense that they can be applied as design rules to create beauty. However, applying the instrumental knowledge and skills as design rules only, does not necessarily lead to an attractive design. To create an attractive design, a designer needs to combine such design rules with a good sense of beauty. This combination of instrumental knowledge and skills and the intuitive sense for aesthetics can be seen as aesthetic literacy.

Although aesthetic literacy might be difficult to describe, that it can be trained is proved by art and design schools. In most Dutch art academies, part of the educational method is critical reflection, in the form of a Socratic dialog, as a means to let the student develop his aesthetic literacy. Through critical reflection, the student learns to verbalize his design process and learning process, which is the basis for a dialogue with their teacher. In that way the 'intuitiveness' becomes explicit and increases students' insight in their (development of) aesthetic literacy. As this instrument of critical reflection appears to be effective for the

development of aesthetic literacy, why wouldn't it be effective for the development of 'emotional literacy' of students in the minor Experience Branding for the benefit of their designing for emotions?

Emotional literacy is a well-known topic in educational research literature with regard to the development of social-emotional skills of children in primary education. Elementary school is an ideal environment for a child to learn how to cope with its own emotions and those of others, to be successful in social interactions. The first step for a child is to become aware of his or her own emotion, and then to control his or her emotion. After that, a child learns to sense emotions of others and to respond to those in an appropriate way. At best, a child learns how to control emotions of others, like comforting another child that is sad (Radke Yarrow & Zahn Waxler, 1984). Then later, in secondary education, pupils refine these emotional skills although emotional literacy is not an explicit part of the curriculum anymore. With regard to the development of emotional literacy in higher education, there is hardly any research literature other than that focusing on emotions as influence on learning processes and study results in general. Also, when looking at emotional literacy as Emotional Intelligence (Goleman, 1996), Emotional Intelligence is seen as a conditional influence on professional results with no relation with the nature of the profession. In other words, Emotional Intelligence has an effect on professional results but is not part of the area of professional skills itself (although Goleman stresses that some elements of Emotional Intelligence are beneficial to certain professions).

In sum, the minor Experience Branding focuses to a great extent on the development of emotional literacy as a professional competency for designing for emotions. The underlying motivation is that with a less developed emotional literacy designers create inferior emotional designs. Or stated otherwise, an experience can only be triggered 'in the user' when he is convinced that the designer, or brand, has sincere intentions. We assume that design for emotions which can not be experienced or imagined by designers themselves, lacks the essentials. For that reason emotional literacy should not be only regarded as an intervening factor, but as an important determining factor for emotional design results (see Figure 1). It is, therefore, interesting to develop an educational method with which emotional literacy can be developed as professional competency to design for emotions.

Figure 1. Emotional literacy as professional competency in emotional design: not an intervening but a determining factor for emotional design.

Method: teaching emotional design

As has been said, the underlying assumption of the current teaching method is the more a designer has developed his emotional literacy, the better he is able to design for emotions. In that way the designer can use his emotional literacy as a professional competency. Furthermore, it is beneficial for designers to have a good understanding of the influence of the cultural background of users on their norms and values as well as their perception of (visual) communication.

Since experiencing personal emotions and those of others is crucial for the development of emotional literacy, Kolb's Experiential Learning Model (Kolb, 1984) appeared to be very useful for our educational method. According to Kolb, learning by experiencing situations and phenomena in life result in strong learning effects. Therefore, the educational method presented in this article, has been organised according to Kolb's Experiential Learning Model. For each of Kolb's elements, we stated particular questions as learning goals for students (Figure 2).

Kolb element	Question	Learning goal
Concrete experience	How can I recognise my own values and emotions?	Self-aware experiencing emotions by the student
Reflective observation	How can I recognise values and emotions of others?	Observe and reflect to emotions of others
Abstract conceptualisation	In what cultural context (with specific norms and values) do users of my design live?	Understand and assimilate knowledge
Active experimentation	Which cultural-specific symbols can I use as a mechanism to evoke emotions?	Active creation of experiences

Figure 2. Elements of the education model for design for emotions plotted on Kolb’s model for Experiential Learning.

Recognising personal emotions

In Kolb’s element of concrete experience, being aware of your emotions is the central theme. To improve his design for emotions, the student as designer, first has to recognise his own emotions. Being aware of experiencing an emotion, and understanding what and how that emotion has been evoked, is the first step to control emotional experience in design. One exercise that students do is to recall 10 meaningful moments in life and to express those moments using images. Another way to let students consciously experience emotions is to have them make notes or sketches in a diary or dummy at hand as soon as a significant experience occurred. Later on students publish these experiences on their weblog.

Recognising emotions of others

In Kolb's element of reflective observation, watching and reflecting on emotions of others are central. Students research the emotions and values of others through observation studies, interviews, or ways of ethnographic research in which people are studied in their natural habitat or being questioned in a natural conversation. Next to that, all students read each other's weblogs where they share their experiences. Also in class, students are confronted with emotions of others in presentations, which they talk about in critical reflective discussions with each other and teachers.

Learning in what cultural context users of design live

In Kolb's element of abstract conceptualisation, thinking is central. Literature discussed in class is in keeping with Hill, (2007), Pine & Gilmore (2000), Jansen, (2006), Franzen & Bouwman (2001), and Modell (2006). With this, students gain knowledge about psychological and physiological aspects of brain and body, consciousness and sub-consciousness, reasoning and intuition, values and emotions, experience economy, branding, and (Western) social-cultural environment. Students are stimulated to find books and articles themselves or to select them from a recommendation list, and to write reviews on these at their weblogs. Another way to make students aware of their experiences and take notice of what is happening in reality has been made explicit by reviewing newspaper articles. Students have to describe actual situations in terms of the meaning these might have to people, from a social-cultural point of view.

Finally, an important event is the individual "Emotional Consult" each student has with one of the teachers. In a critical-reflective dialog, they investigate what personal fascination the student has and how that is related to the profession of Experience Branding with the aim to help the student connect his professional insight with his personal emotional literacy.

Use of cultural-specific symbols to evoke emotions

In Kolb's element of active experimentation, acting and creating is central. Eventually the student has to create a meaningful experience. To touch a group of users, the student should use a visual vocabulary and cultural-specific symbols, which are recognised by users and to evoke emotions. One exercise here is to create an archetype. This exercise is inspired by the model of Jansen (2006) for the creation of successful brands by positioning those as Jungian archetypes. For this, students have to think of specific (visual) cultural symbols that express certain values, which are commonly perceived and recognised. As a final and large assignment, students are

challenged to develop a meaningful brand experience for an existing or fake brand in which all knowledge, skills and experiences from the former stages are applied.

Findings

Since every student has been asked to create a weblog, we collected a large online resource of students work mingled with personal notes of students reflecting their view on life (n=37). In this section we present some examples of students work, illustrating the value of the method.

Recognising and understanding personal emotions

The assignment '10 meaningful moments in life' brought two valuable insights. First, students started to think consciously about moments in their life which were meaningful, moments which left a sustainable imprint that transformed the student's idea about life. Second, students were challenged to express these moments in life visually in images that could be interpreted in such way that peers could envision the experience. In other words, they were enforced to make this a 'collective' experience to be shared with their peers (Figure 3).

For each student, these are very private feelings and next to that, creating and sharing those emotional experiences makes them even more aware of those feelings.

Figure 3. Example of visualisation of 10 moments in life. Student Sarah visualised her feelings about the transformation from girl to woman.

Publishing experiences on their weblogs resulted in 1 or 2 posting per week per student. In some of these posts, students describe the experience of feeling an emotion. For example, a student named Arjen, reports his experience in conquering his fear for heights. Together with some other students he visited Rotterdam's Euromast, a 186 meter high monument. At a certain level, one can climb stairs to higher levels. Arjen describes it like this: "What was most impressive

was the stairs to the second platform. Actually, I can only recall that I was focused completely at the absence of a handrail. [...] I realized my brain focused only on getting up the stairs safely and ignoring the rest of the situation. The panorama view was superb, and the feeling that I conquered my fear too. [...] Most interesting was to experience how your body handles situations like this. The view came second in place. This intense experience this is something I won't easily forget."

Recognising and understanding emotions of others

Figure 4 shows the picture of two students; one conquering his fear of heights, the other sharing his emotions. This is an example of how students observe each other as study objects which students do more and more during the course.

Figure 4. Arjen at the left, conquered his fear of heights. Igor at the right, shares his emotions.

Presentations about personal experiences of students also provide insight in emotional experiences of others. Once, student Asmidin talked about his 10 meaningful moments in life. He talked about perceiving his rock band as family (instead of his real family) and also about his learning process to become a tattoo-artist. On a certain moment one of the boys in the band said to him: "As soon as you are skilled enough to make your first tattoo, I want to have that from you." This explains the deepest feeling of friendship or bonding, as well as the value one feels for a gift of a friend. Also, at the time of telling this story to his peers, the student became aware of these feeling and value of friendship, and at the same time, his sudden awareness was witnessed by his peers who were deeply impressed.

Other ways in which students get insight from other people is by doing field research in such way that people can be observed and questioned in a natural setting. Sarah, exploring people's motivation for online social networks, like the Dutch Hyves, describes this approach on her weblog:

“I was at the birthday party of my nephew. Initially I talked with a few people about the weather, cleaning supplies and other random stuff people talk about when they are at birthday parties. But suddenly I heard a friend of my nephew say: “Gerrit, do you have Hyves?” The rest of the evening I spent my time chatting with a few people about their Hyves accounts, explained why I asked so many questions and found that they were very open about the most mundane details. By having my nephew as a common factor we were not complete strangers and my study objects seemed to enjoy talking about the subject as opposed to the state of the weather last week. After the birthday party I used the same tactic with friends [...] And I repeated this every time I saw an opportunity. [...] And, as a last note, I would like to add that I believe the openness created by them knowing somebody I also know (thus, not being complete strangers) helped in getting more open answers.”

Learning in what cultural context (with specific norms and values) users of design live

Reflections of students show that the course book helped them to frame their experiences and observations. As one of them, Asia, states: “It gives me a structure, and helps me to decide what to do to get things done”. Also, the theoretical information has provided students a clear understanding in the meaning of brands on their personal life and people in general as well as the position that brands take in society. Another student, Arjen, says: “I was amazed by my own ignorance. It amazed me how deeply influenced I was by brands. Now I know what power one can use to influence people.” Next to that, students indicated that they now are able to define the emotional interaction between a product (brand) and a person.

Use of cultural-specific symbols to evoke emotions

The archetype assignment resulted in a variety of images. Student Igor made two creations of the Outlaw archetype (Figure 5). By using a set of classic symbols (Western cowboy attributes) and modern symbols (urban gangster attributes) he managed to express the archetype in different visuals but loaded with the same meaning.

Figure 5. Archetype assignment: classic and modern cultural-specific symbols of an outlaw

Another student, Judith, created an experience with the Explorer archetype (Figure 6). Based on a book she knows from her childhood, she created an Explorer archetype in the form of a virtual character in a combination of online media such as a traveller’s website, a Flickr-photopage and text-messages. She succeeded in keeping her teachers in wondering who this Bennie Blauw was who send them a text-message, which is a means of connection between people. Even on the visit of the traveller’s webpage, it took sometime before it was revealed that we dealt with a virtual character instead of a real life person. This was a convincing experience that suggested that a real person wanted to share his travel adventures with friends.

Figure 6. Archetype assignment: Explorer Bennie Blauw in Japan

Some of the former cohort students (the current cohort has not reached that phase yet) are currently graduating with the design of meaningful brand experiences such as engagement of student volunteers for sustainable tuk-tuks (three-wheel taxis) in India, enforcing brand loyalty through new media for fashion brand Mexx, and merging the physical and virtual presence of a social network of sustainable dance club WATT in Rotterdam.

Conclusions and discussion

Inspired by Kolb's Experiential Learning Model and with the instrument of critical reflection, an educational method has been developed for students to develop their emotional literacy as professional competency in order to become better designers for emotions. The variety of assignments that students work on, address all elements of Kolb's model: feeling, observing, thinking and acting (creating). They train their awareness of their own emotions as well as emotions of others, and they are able to express these experiences verbally or textually to peers and teachers. With the use of knowledge gained from books, articles and lectures, students gain understanding of how real-life phenomena are meaningful for people. At the end, the students integrate all these competencies into a professional craftsmanship for designing for emotions.

Although the curriculum of the course is based on user-centered design, the educational method focuses on the development of a personal ability into a professional competency. The latter is quite common at art academies, but less for design institutes.

Feedback from students illustrates the minor's value and its meaningfulness for the students. For example, Esther, states: "I can't recall in which moment it exactly started, but one thing is for sure, [the minor] Experience Branding has changed my life."

Although first results are promising, we did not assess the effects of our educational method to emotional literacy as professional design competency. We therefore plan a baseline study and repeated measurements to get insight in students' development of emotional literacy. Also, differences between the emotional literacy between the minor Experience Branding and other minors will be taken into account.

In sum, the current approach provides lots of insights in emotional literacy, but also evokes some new questions that should be taken into account. First, we wonder if it is the history of Dutch design tradition that led to design being a well-developed profession in the Netherlands. Dutch art academies and design institutes have contributed to that for years. Dutch designers are known for their expressive and remarkable designs. Is it because of this freedom from 'design rules' that the Dutch design students are easily stimulated in their emotional literacy in the way we described in this article? Secondly, is there a minimum level of starting qualifications one should have to be trained with this method to become a professional emotional designer, and to what extent can these qualifications be identified and measured?

In our educational method, critical reflection is a key pedagogical instrument. The success of this instrument in making students aware of their own and others emotions, to express them to others and to listen to each other's most private stories, might be explained by the Dutch mentality. Dutch society is known for tolerance, in which one is not easily embarrassed by other people's behaviour, opinions and beliefs. Also, the Netherlands is known for its emancipated and egalitarian culture with a liberated morality (for example, in matters of sexuality) that prevents people feeling offended, and where teachers and students are at almost the same level in hierarchy or social status. When this is true, the educational method can be more effective for students with a similar mentality.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank our students Sarah, Esther, Arjen, Igor, Asmidin, Asia, and Judith for sharing their illustrations, portraits, and experiences that we used in this paper.

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